

DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCIES IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The development of acmeological competences in preparing future teachers for professional activity will give a high result if: the level of study of the problem of acmeological development methods is analyzed; if the pedagogical and psychological aspects of professional adaptation of future teachers are studied; if the pedagogical conditions ensuring the effectiveness of acmeological development of future teachers are determined; based on a systematic approach, a model for preparing future educators for professional activity was developed and put into practice.*

Keywords: *philosophical, pedagogical observation, pedagogical, methodical and pedagogical educational modeling; psychological; pedagogical experience; person; self-awareness.*

In any field or profession, it is important for a person to develop his acmeological competencies in order to have his place in the society and in various district situations in it. In the theory of personality, there are views on the unique professional acmeological competencies of a person in the fields of pedagogy and psychology. However, in the current modern technology and technological era, the increasing influence of the means on the human mind puts the above issue on the agenda. In order to obtain the efficiency and high results of every work, the personnel with strong, sharp knowledge, high talent, adaptability to the demands of the times, organizational culture, behavior, motivation and inclination to acquire knowledge are very necessary. It is not possible to fully achieve a specific goal, such as those who are skillful and intelligent, able to work intelligently, mature specialists of their profession, rather than technologies with many new opportunities. That's why long-term experience acquisition, formation of skills and qualifications aimed at human perception, intelligence, human professional skill formation is the main factor of long-term priority activity of any organization.

Today's most advanced corporations pay special attention to training their personnel on the basis of modern knowledge, improving their qualifications, creating conditions for their work and working as a whole team.

Today, young people enter the workforce based on their specializations, but long-term practical processes are required to increase their qualification indicators, knowledge, and talent accordingly.

Qualified specialist: it is becoming an urgent issue to determine the possibilities and results of the labor activity by determining the suitability for the profession, psychological readiness, depending on the type of work, the level of social responsibility, its process and results. Reflexive - innovation is studied by improving the potential to the level of skill and determining the social significance of innovations, based on the aspirations spent and the achievements of its implementation. According to the reflective aspect: (related to the self-awareness of the self as a

developing "I" and the ability to understand communication partners in the process of work) considering the system-creating factor, the optimal interaction of acmeological aspects in determining the professionalization of a person provides

It should be assumed that ability and talent develop in an organic sequence with each other. The research object of acmeology is an acme person, i.e. a mature person, based on objective laws, in the process of studying the methodological, technological and humanitarian aspects of professional activity and creative activity, he determines the acmeological problems related to the material and spiritual aspects of the profession in the development of society. . Today, in the development of market relations, the formation of new professions, the cultivation of mature personnel corresponding to the requirements of the time is one of the urgent issues. A creative complex approach to the processes of globalization, the culture of professionalism, the analysis of the views of scholars and thinkers in the direction of perfection and perfection, the aspects specific to national and universal human values and the deep acquisition of modern experience, the issues of mastering technology, technology and information culture can also become one of the objects of acmeology. Human abilities In fact, it knows no bounds, but it is not a finding that just appears in a limitless source, but it requires a long process of learning and improving acmeological abilities, that is, science, art, sports, profession in general in certain areas or directions of a person. In general, it encompasses both the physical and spiritual aspects of human activity. A person's psychological character, temperament, sense of understanding the world, worldview, and other characteristics create a special inclination in a person for a profession and a craft. artistic image, human is divided into techniques. Based on this, in educating our youth, it is necessary to direct them to acquire knowledge, taking into account their capabilities, abilities and, most importantly, their interests. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the implementation of education on the basis of proven experiences of the world. In many educational systems of the world, the system of adaptation to the social environment and the system of mutual actions are being taught and professional knowledge is being taught. The field of acmeology, in which the sciences that study this system, learn to enrich themselves with new approaches, principles, methods and views, is precisely the field of acmeology that seeks ways to reach the level of perfection. It studies the phenomenology, laws and mechanisms of human development, natural, social, The science of acmeology, which appeared in the integration of humanitarian and technical sciences, belongs to the same science. The science of acmeology, which is developing in interaction with sociology, pedagogy and psychology, has recently been paying attention to the training of qualified specialists and the continuous education system. Taking into account various aspects of personnel retraining and improving their skills with the help of developing acmeological competencies, the problems of opening and developing the creative abilities of qualified specialists are coming to the fore. In this regard, much attention is paid to the personality of the teacher in the education system. If the acmeological competences of future teachers are studied in terms of professional activity, it can be found that the person of a mature teacher, who is in accordance with the requirements of today's time, but also has deep knowledge of the past, his work The process of training a specialist is a very complex pedagogical and psychological process. The training of qualified specialists who educate the young generation is an important priority issue. Even today, attention is paid to the issue of continuous work and search of the teacher's personality. On the basis of acmeological competences, striving for the acme level of one's activity and realizing it requires a new method and everyone to follow their own directions. The idea of an individual method and option of self-

realization (K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, A.A. Derkach, etc.). The received professional competences and the level of temporary competence achieved by a person are largely determined by the individual psychological characteristics and characteristics of future teachers. According to A.A. Derkach, the need to refer to the model in acmeology is to help us imagine a psychological phenomenon, its important features, allows to reveal structural features, mechanisms, levels of formation.

According to the reflective side: (identity of the person as a developing "I". Understanding and communication partners in the process of work related to the ability to understand) a person is considered a system-creating factor optimal interaction of acmeological aspects in determining professionalization provides. When teaching a school-age child, the young generation, and other listeners, a teacher who can be a highly professional person must be able to fully engage the listener under his influence and prepare him for learning and life skills. . It is necessary to take into account the structural aspects of acmeological approaches in the training of qualified specialists based on the implementation of acmeological educational technologies in the practice of training, the reflexive-psychological concept of the development of education and creativity.

In fact, Abdulla Avloni has a wide range of personal and professional qualities of a teacher by defining: personal qualities of the educator, i.e. moral, polite, knowledgeable, intelligence, ingenuity, prudence, intelligence for the educational process. The main basis is the creative search for a new form and style of reading and teaching.

It shows that the search for tools is one of the most important professional qualities of a teacher. With this, Abdulla Avloni promotes a relatively acmeological approach to the teacher's activity in the image of his time. Another important aspect of the process of development of acmeological competences of future teachers is the complex of necessary conditions for the acquisition and full application of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications in the above-mentioned directions. is determined. Because a comfortable and goal-oriented pedagogical environment facilitates the achievement of the desired result from the process.

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